

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1a–j

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C.	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					O	H	N
1a	C ₆ H ₅	158	62	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	58.10 (58.81)	4.18 (4.15)	22.15 (22.21)
1b	<i>o</i> -OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	151	61	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	58.99 (54.01)	4.85 (4.87)	21.69 (21.72)
1c	<i>m</i> -OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	124	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	58.98 (54.01)	4.86 (4.87)	21.61 (21.72)
1d	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	185	64	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	58.97 (54.01)	4.82 (4.87)	21.67 (21.72)
1e	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	152	59	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Cl	50.80 (50.54)	3.82 (3.78)	21.02 (21.05)
1f	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	182	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Cl	50.45 (50.54)	3.76 (3.78)	20.96 (21.05)
1g	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	185	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Cl	50.14 (50.54)	3.88 (3.78)	20.99 (21.05)
1h	<i>o</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	158	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₁₁ S ₂	49.68 (49.76)	3.75 (3.72)	22.88 (22.80)
1i	<i>o</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	167	78	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	52.41 (52.70)	4.80 (4.27)	21.12 (21.20)
1j	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	180	81	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂	52.40 (52.70)	4.26 (4.27)	21.11 (21.20)

Biological screening : The antibacterial activity of **1** was determined against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* at the concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹ of acetone following the agar plate method⁵. Amongst the compounds tested, **1b** was found to exhibit relatively higher activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition 1.5 and 1.0 mm, respectively), **1h** was more active against *S. aureus* than *E. coli* (zone of inhibition 1.0 and 0.5 mm, respectively), and **1e** was inactive against *S. aureus* but it caused the inhibition of *E. coli* (zone of inhibition 1.0 mm). Minimum activity was found in **1a** and **1j** (zone of inhibition for both types of bacteria being same, i.e. 0.5 mm).

All the compounds tested show practically very poor activity compared to the activity of sulphamethoxypyridazine against bacteria, which further proves that *N*⁴-substitution of sulphonamide does not prove advantageous according to PABA mechanism. The little activity in spite of this can be attributed to *p*-methoxyanilino and arylthioureido moieties.

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Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-II. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Benzoylamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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1, 3,4-Oxadiazoles are known to exhibit a wide spectrum of physiological properties¹. Thymol derivatives have also been reported to possess physiological properties². Keeping this in view, some new 2,5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles bearing thymol moiety of type **4** have been synthesised (Scheme 1).

Thymol was condensed with chloroacetic acid and esterified (**1**) which was treated with hydrazine hydrate to get the hydrazide (**2**). The hydrazide (**2**) on treatment with cyanogenbromide gave 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives which were condensed with different acid chlorides to get 2-benzoylamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**4**) (Table 1). The structure of the product has been characterised by ir and nmr spectral data (Tables 2 and 3).

R = Aryl
Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C
1.	Phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	144
2.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	199
3.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	186
4.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	192
5.	2-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₃ O ₂	88
6.	3-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₃ O ₂	98
7.	4-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₃ O ₂	93
8.	3-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	112
9.	4-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	208
10.	Cinnamyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	119
11.	Hydrocinnamyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	104
12.	3-Pyridyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂	98
13.	4-Pyridyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂	105
14.	2 : 4-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	219
15.	2 : 6-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	119
16.	3 : 5-Dinitrosalicyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₆	181
17.	2-Acetoxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	110
18.	3 : 4 : 5-Trihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₆	98

* C, H and N analyses found satisfactory.

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF COMPOUNDS 4

Sl. no.*	NH	C=O	C=N	C-O-C	Substituent R
1.	3 160	1 730	1 670	1 160	—
2.	Overlap with OH str.	1 730	1 610	1 160	3 250br(OH)
3.	Overlap with OH	1 720	1 610	1 160	3 240br(OH)
4.	Overlap with OH	1 730	1 600	1 150	3 260br(OH)
5.	3 150	1 710	1 610	1 170	—
6.	3 160	1 715	1 610	1 160	—
7.	3 160	1 710	1 610	1 160	—
8.	3 165	1 720	1 620	1 160	1 580s, 1 350s(NO ₂)
9.	3 160	1 710	1 620	1 160	1 575s, 1 355s(NO ₂)
10.	3 150	1 710	1 620	1 160	—
11.	3 155	1 710	1 625	1 160	—
12.	3 150	1 730	1 610	1 160	—
13.	3 150	1 725	1 615	1 160	—
14.	Overlap with OH	1 730	1 610	1 140	3 200br(OH)
15.	Overlap with OH	1 725	1 615	1 150	3 250br(OH)
16.	Overlap with OH	1 680	1 630	1 160	3 350br(OH), 1 570(s), 1 310s(NO ₂)
17.	3 150	1 710	1 610	1 170	1 735(COOH ₂)
18.	Overlap with OH	1 700	1 600	1 150	3 275br(OH)

* Compounds refer as Sl. no. in Table 1.

Antimicrobial activity: The 2-benzoylamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy)methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity by cup-plate method^{1,2} at a concentration of 100 µg ml⁻¹ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus citreus* and gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhosa*. The antifungal testing was carried out with *Neurospora crassa* and *Aspergillus niger*. The activities were compared with chloromycetin.

Maximum antibacterial activity (18–20 mm zone of inhibition) was observed in phenyl, nitrophenyl, cinnamyl and 3,4,5-trihydroxyphenyl derivatives against *S. typhosa* and good activity (16–18 mm) was observed in oxadiazole derivatives bearing 3-hydroxyphenyl, 3-chlorophenyl, 2 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl, 2 : 6-dihydroxyphenyl, 3-pyridyl, 4-pyridyl moiety. Maximum antifungal activity (18–20 mm zone of inhibition) was observed in compounds bearing 4-hydroxyphenyl, 2-chlorophenyl, 3-chlorophenyl and 3-pyridyl moiety against *A. niger*, while good activity (16–18 mm zone of inhibition) was observed with compounds bearing R=3-nitrophenyl, hydrocinnamyl, 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl, 2,6-dihydroxyphenyl and 2-acetoxyphenyl.

TABLE 3—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF SELECTED COMPOUNDS 4

Sl. no.	R	(OH) ₂ CH (6H, d)	CH ₂ -Ar (3H, s)	(OH) ₂ CH (1H, m)	ArOCH ₂ (2H, s)	ArH (m)	Substituent R
1.	Phenyl	1.08	2.15	2.80–3.70	4.55	6.50–7.10	—
2.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	1.14	2.13	2.86–3.49	5.54	6.60–8.20	4.79(1H, s, OH)
3.	4-Chlorophenyl	1.09	2.16	2.84–3.24	5.07	6.63–7.21	—
4.	3-Pyridyl	1.06	2.17	2.81–3.28	5.01	6.70–7.21	—
5.	3-Nitrophenyl	1.07	2.17	2.82–3.28	5.07	6.65–7.21	—
6.	3 : 5-Dinitrosalicyl	1.04	2.16	2.84–3.28	5.05	6.90–8.00	—

Experimental

2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetylhydrazide: A mixture of 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetate (0.01 mol) in methanol (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 0.01 mol) was refluxed on a waterbath for 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from hot water, (76%), m.p. 78° (Found: C, 64.4; H, 8.00; N, 12.58. $C_{15}H_{18}O_2N_2$ calcd. for: C, 64.80; H, 8.11; N, 12.61%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH asym.), 3 200 (NH sym.), 1 680 (C=C) and 1 250 cm^{-1} (C-O-C)⁴.

2-Amino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole: A mixture of 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetylhydrazide (0.01 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath at 60° for 1.5 h and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (72%), m.p. 155° (Found: C, 62.95; H, 6.48; N, 12.65. $C_{15}H_{17}O_2N_3$ calcd. for: C, 63.15; H, 6.88; N, 12.95%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 150 (NH), 1 660 (C=N) and 1 160 cm^{-1} (C-O-C ether linkage)⁴.

2-Benzoylamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles: A mixture of 2-amino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.01 mol) and benzoylchloride (0.01 mol) was condensed in the presence of pyridine (2.3 ml) at 80° in a water-bath for 1 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (72%), m.p. 144° (Found: C, 68.30; H, 5.94; N, 11.94. $C_{20}H_{21}O_2N_3$ calcd. for: C, 68.37; H, 5.98; N, 11.96%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 160 (NH), 1 730 (C=O), 1 670 (C=N) and 1 160 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); δ (DMSO d_6) 1.08 (6H, d, $(CH_2)_2CH$), 2.15 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.80-3.70 (1H, m, $(CH_2)_2CH$), 4.55 (2H, s, $ArOCH_2$) and 6.50-7.10 (m, ArH).

Similarly, other substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared (Table 1).

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Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-X. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-5-p-phenylsulphophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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2,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have been found to possess a wide spectrum of biological properties¹. The present communication deals with the preparation of some 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (4) with an intention to get better therapeutic agents.

p-Carbomethoxydiphenyl sulphone (2) was esterified with absolute methanol and condensed with hydrazine hydrate to get *p*-hydrazinocarbonyldiphenyl sulphone (3). Hydrazide on condensation with different aromatic acids in presence of phosphorous oxychloride gave the 2-aryl-5-*p*-phenylsulphophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (4). The structures of the compounds (Table 1) were based on their

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1.	Phenyl	175	77	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_2S$
2.	3-Tolyl	189	69	$C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_2S$
3.	4-Tolyl	216	74	$C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_2S$
4.	2-Chlorophenyl	183	72	$C_{20}H_{13}ClN_2O_2S$
5.	3-Chlorophenyl	163	68	$C_{20}H_{13}ClN_2O_2S$
6.	4-Chlorophenyl	216	82	$C_{20}H_{13}ClN_2O_2S$
7.	2-Aminophenyl	113	58	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2S$
8.	3-Aminophenyl	196	52	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2S$
9.	4-Aminophenyl	190	62	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2S$
10.	2-Nitrophenyl	186	79	$C_{20}H_{13}N_3O_4S$
11.	3-Nitrophenyl	159	80	$C_{20}H_{13}N_3O_4S$
12.	4-Nitrophenyl	243	84	$C_{20}H_{13}N_3O_4S$
13.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	256	72	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_4S$
14.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	193	68	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_4S$
15.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	298	79	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_4S$
16.	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	203	68	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_6S$
17.	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	226	58	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_6S$
18.	3,5-Dihydroxyphenyl	214	61	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_6S$
19.	3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	138	66	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_7S$
20.	1-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl	282	72	$C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_3S$
21.	2-Hydroxy-3-naphthyl	290	78	$C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_3S$
22.	2-Methoxyphenyl	143	71	$C_{21}H_{18}N_2O_3S$
23.	2,3-Dimethoxyphenyl	187	76	$C_{22}H_{20}N_2O_4S$
24.	2-Acetyloxyphenyl	177	67	$C_{22}H_{18}N_2O_5S$
25.	Benzoylaminoethyl	293	64	$C_{23}H_{17}N_2O_3S$
26.	Benzyl	104	58	$C_{23}H_{19}N_2O_2S$
27.	1-Methylphenyl	135	52	$C_{23}H_{19}N_2O_2S$
28.	2-Phenethyl	155	59	$C_{23}H_{21}N_2O_2S$
29.	3-Pyridyl	228	62	$C_{19}H_{13}N_3O_2S$
30.	4-Pyridyl	214	63	$C_{19}H_{13}N_3O_2S$
31.	4-Bromophenyl	196	72	$C_{20}H_{13}BrN_2O_2S$